
| RESEARCH ARTICLE

Ultrasonic-Enabled Smart Medicine Dispenser: Low-Cost IoT Solution for Medication Adherence in Resource-Constrained Settings

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| ARTICLE INFORMATION

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| ABSTRACT

The growing complexity of patient medication management necessitates more efficient solutions and dependable tracking mechanisms to enhance healthcare outcomes. The model provides the results of a smart system created using the Internet of Things (IoT) to offer patients extensive medication management, which will guarantee consistent medication intake and reduce the likelihood of mistakes. The system uses an Arduino Uno as the central controller and attached to an RTC module to keep track of time, an ultrasonic sensor used to identify the box movements and an I2C interface LCD to show vital information. They have push buttons so that the users can interact. The suggested system is planned to alert patients to avoid skipped doses. Simple alerts, like beeps and lights, can help patients recall the time to administer their medication this way, making it easier to adhere to their treatment plan, not to skip doses, and receive affordable and effective healthcare assistance. This research creates the basis for the development of intelligent healthcare systems.

| KEYWORDS

Arduino Uno, healthcare technology, Internet of Things, medication monitoring, patient medication management, real-time monitoring

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I. INTRODUCTION

The problem of medication non-adherence has become one of the burning issues in the medical field over the past years, especially among elderly patients and those with chronic diseases. Factors like forgetfulness, lack of awareness regarding the timing of dosage and reliance on the nurses all play a part in missed/incorrect intake of medicine. This usually results in serious health maladies, more hospitalizations and unnecessary medical expenses. This consequently leads to an increased necessity to have intelligent systems that may assist patients to be more precise and independent in following their treatment plans [1], [2]. Internet of Things (IoT) technologies have demonstrated potential benefits in the context of healthcare to help overcome these challenges. The IoT-connected systems allow monitoring medical devices in real-time, automation, and remote interaction. A number of authors have created smart medicine dispensers and pillboxes with microcontrollers, alarms, sensor, and mobile applications that tell users when to take medicine at the right time [3], [4]. The NFC-based inventory tracking, biometric authentication, and cloud-based medication management systems to allow remote caregivers are other innovations [5], [6]. Nevertheless, the majority of available solutions are either too complicated to use by the elderly or do not offer an essential feature such as real-time monitoring of the level of medicine and adaptive alert mechanisms [7], [8]. In order to address these shortcomings, this paper suggests an all-inclusive and convenient IoT-based medication monitoring system. The system is constructed on an Arduino Uno microcontroller and this is coupled with a Real time clock (rtc) to maintain time and schedule, ultrasonic sensor to detect medicine availability, I2C-based LCD display to provide information to the user and push buttons are used to provide manual input. The system gives the patient timely alerts by providing a low-cost, scalable, and efficient, easily accessible, healthcare service, this work will enhance medication adherence, minimize human error, and support independent living, especially of the elderly [9]–[11].

II. MOTIVATION

When it comes to elderly and chronically ill patients, medication non-adherence is a particularly significant problem since older individuals tend to forget or become confused [1]. The existing solutions mostly consist of reminders or remote monitoring solutions, and so far, they have not worked with regards to the detection of real time medicine levels, cost, and convenience [3], [5]. Not only are they complex and expensive, but range is also a constraint in rural situation, and particularly in the design of the interface and excessive cost

and then as stated constraining in rural [2]. This project is driven by the necessity to have a simple, cheap, and holistic system that facilitates real-time monitoring, and ease of work, therefore, enhancing medication compliance and reducing human error.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many old and chronically sick people experience a problem with taking their drugs because they forget about it and do not have a supervisor [1]. Currently available IoT-based pillboxes provide reminders but frequently lack real-time monitoring of medicine levels and adaptive scheduling [3], [4]. Furthermore, the high expenses and complicated interfaces restrict their practicality in rural or resource-constrained areas [6], [8]. Hence, there is a need for an affordable, user-friendly IoT solution that provides timely alerts and effective medication management [9].

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

The incorporation of IoT into healthcare has resulted in various advancements in patient monitoring and medication management. Shetty et al. [1] conducted a thorough analysis of health systems that employ temperature, ECG, and blood pressure sensors for continuous real-time monitoring of biomedical data. Bhuiyan et al. [2] suggested a healthcare model that can be implemented in both rural and urban settings, utilizing wireless sensor networks and real-time data transmission.

In the context of medication management, Gaikwad et al. [3] developed a smart medicine box using LEDs, servomotors, and the Blynk platform for scheduled alerts. Challa et al. [4] developed a system using an Arduino Uno and NodeMCU-based platform for basic pill-time reminders. Patil et al. [5] expanded on this by incorporating NFC-based inventory tracking and integrating a mobile app, which further increased user engagement. Fuad et al. [6] integrated fingerprint recognition for secure access and temperature sensors to ensure the proper storage of medicines.

Khan et al. [7] develop a smart pill box that was cloud based, but lack of medication level monitoring. Srinivas et al [8] implement ESP8266 pill access detector module connected with magnetic reed switches. The recent improvements use AI to manage medication timings and sent alerts, as seen in Ramesh et al. [9], and real-time notifications integrated with mobile applications. [10] proposed a low cost device that aims to encourage medication adherence for the people with chronic conditions.

These models fail to offer the best solution, for the correct level of medication intake, user interaction and alerts at the time of medication. This research aims to fill these gaps and develop an easy-to-use medication monitoring box that is based on Internet of Things (IoT)

technology to enhance medication adherence and timely taking of prescribed medications and continuous monitoring.

V. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

Arduino Uno, RTC Module, Ultrasonic Sensor, I2C LCD Display

A. Arduino Uno

Arduino Uno is a well-known microcontroller which is based on ATmega328P, a microcontroller that is easy to integrate with embedded system applications, as shown in figure 1. It has 14 digital input/output pins, 6 analog input pins and a 16 MHz crystal oscillator. The board has a USB interface to simply program and communicate and has voltage regulators allowing the board to operate with variety of power sources. It has open source hardware and software platform and is best in rapid development of prototypes. Also, it can be easily configured with a variety of sensors and the Arduino IDE(Integrated Development Environment) simplifies the development process. The Arduino Uno board is used for many real time Internet of Things(IoT) based applications and commonly used in academic institutions and projects because of inexpensive, it can be easily powered by low voltage and it is easy to use.

Fig. 1. Arduino Uno Board

B. RTC Module

The DS3231 is a highly precise real-time clock (RTC) module that consistently keeps track of time and date information, as illustrated in Fig. 2. It enables smooth communication with microcontrollers such as the Arduino Uno. The module includes a temperature-compensated crystal oscillator (TCXO), which helps maintain accurate timing by compensating for any changes in temperature. Even during power outages, the onboard CR2032 battery ensures that the clock continues to function. The DS3231 is commonly employed in time-critical

scenarios like alarms, data logging, and medication scheduling because of its dependability, low power usage, and compact size.

Fig. 2. RTC Module

C. Ultrasonic Sensor

The ultrasonic sensor is a device that measures distance using sonar technology, as depicted in Figure 3. It emits high-frequency sound waves from the transmitter and measures the time it takes for the echo to bounce back to the receiver. This sensor is perfect for monitoring the remaining quantity of medicine in containers or compartments. With a typical measuring range of 2cm to 400cm, the sensor allows for non-contact detection, making it a hygienic and dependable solution in healthcare and monitoring systems. It functions effectively with 5V DC and is compatible with a wide range of Arduino boards.

Fig. 3. Ultrasonic Sensor

D. I2C LCD Display

The 16x2 I2C LCD display is an alphanumeric screen capable of displaying 16 characters on 2 lines, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The I2C interface significantly reduces the number of pins required to interface with the microcontroller from 12 to just 2 (SDA and SCL). This compact and power-efficient module is ideal for presenting real-time information such as current time,

medication reminders, and sensor readings. It allows better interaction with the user through the displayed data. The LCD Display has low power consumption and user-friendly connection. It is commonly used in embedded systems and in healthcare applications.

Fig. 4. I2C LCD Display

VI. PROPOSED WORK

A. System Methodology

1. Initialization and Time Tracking: The Arduino Uno start all the components connected to it, including the RTC (DS3231), which continuously measures the time to ensure that medication is taken on time.
2. Medication Timing: The system compares the real-time clock values with the medication times set by the user using RTC module.
3. Alert Activation: when the clock time matches with medication time, the buzzer sounds, LED is on at particular slot and LCD displays the medication slot.
4. User Interaction: It waits for the user to open the medication box and this action is detected by the ultrasonic sensor.
5. Acknowledgment and Reset: Once the box has been confirmed to have been opened and closed, the alert (buzzer and LED off) stops and the system resets for the next dose.
6. Continuous Monitoring: The loop keeps running every time a dose is due, making sure the patient takes their medication on time and lowering the chance of forgetting a dose.

B. Hardware Configuration

Arduino Uno: Controls how sensors send information and how outputs like alarms and screens show information.

RTC Module: The RTC Module (DS3231) helps the device keep track of time accurately so that alerts can be sent at the exact times when medication is supposed to be taken.

Ultrasonic Sensor: The sensor that uses sound waves can tell if the box with medicine is open or closed by how the user acts. Then, it stops the messages and changes the system for the next time the user needs medicine.

Push Buttons: Patients or caregivers can use them to respond to reminders or manually activate specific functions, such as setting the time or turning off alerts.

16x2 I2C LCD Display: The LCD display shows the time, alerts, and instructions to the user. It communicates with the Arduino via I2C to reduce wiring complexity. The mower can operate cordlessly because all of its components are powered by a rechargeable battery.

Buzzer: A device that makes sounds to tell patients when they need to take their medicine.

LED Indicator: The LED light shows which medicine is in the slot. The patient can quickly find the right compartment, which is helpful when they have trouble hearing or need more focus.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of the IoT-based patient medication monitoring system.

C. Software Implementation

Programming Environment and Peripheral Integration: You can write code for Arduino Uno using a software called Arduino IDE. The code is written in a language called C/C++. The code starts and controls how the device talks to all the parts that are connected to it. A sensor that uses sound waves, a screen that shows numbers and letters, a speaker that makes a sound, and a light that can turn on or off. You can watch, adjust, and add parts to the system as you use it.

Real-Time Scheduling: The software continuously reads real-time data from the DS3231 RTC and compares it with predefined medication times.

Sensor-Based User Acknowledgment and Loop Execution: An ultrasonic sensor detects when the patient opens the medication box. The system shuts off all notifications and restarts for

the next dose after verification. This continuous loop mechanism ensures dependable, real-time drug adherence with minimal user involvement.

D. Execution Procedure

1. System Setup: The Arduino Uno sets up all the connected components, such as the RTC module, ultrasonic sensor, LCD, buzzer, push buttons, and LED.
2. Alarm Clock Configuration: The user configures the alarm time for medication by inputting a pre-determined code or using push buttons.

Fig. 6. Flow chart of Proposed methodology

3. Time Tracking: The RTC module consistently monitors the present time.
4. Time Comparison: The Arduino verifies if the current RTC time aligns with the predetermined alarm time.
5. Alert Trigger:

When a match is detected:

- A. The alarm goes off to notify the patient.
- B. The medication slot on the LCD is indicated by the corresponding medication.
- C. The LED is switched on to signify an active reminder.

6. Medication Confirmation:

Box opened: The system suspends and evaluates whether the medicine container has been opened.

Box sealed: Once the box is opened, the system checks if the box is properly closed again.

7. Restart and Power Off: If the box is securely sealed, the LED is switched off, and the system resets and waits for the next scheduled alarm.

8. Loop Continuation: The entire process repeats for each scheduled medication time to guarantee adherence.

VII. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The IoT-based medication monitoring system has been successfully implemented and tested. The system followed a fixed schedule and sounded an alarm and turned on the light for the right compartment when it was due. Fig. 7 shows the medication box, which contains the LCD and user input interface arranged neatly on the front side. The alert system turned on when the patient needed to take their medicine. It showed them which slot to use.

Fig. 7. Medication box

To ensure patient contact, the device uses an ultrasonic sensor placed above the medication compartments to detect the presence of a hand within a predefined range. When the scheduled time comes, the LCD displays the medication slot, a buzzer sounds, and an LED illuminates inside the active compartment. When the system detects the hand, it confirms that the medication was consumed and resets for the next dose. Fig. 8 shows the inside of the box, including the red indication LEDs for active doses, compartments, and the ultrasonic sensor for monitoring.

Fig. 8. Internal layout showing medicine slots and alert LED

VIII. CONCLUSION

This system enhances medication adherence by guaranteeing timely alerts and patient response monitoring. It makes use of dependable parts like the ultrasonic sensor, 16x2 I2C LCD, buzzer, and DS3231 RTC module. In order to verify medication intake, the ultrasonic sensor detects hand movement, and the system sounds and displays visual alerts when a predetermined time is reached. It automatically resets for the subsequent dose after confirmation. This lowers the possibility of missed doses and eliminates the need for manual monitoring. It is appropriate for both home and clinical settings due to its small size and low

power consumption. It provides an effective and user-friendly solution for daily medication management, and its low cost and simplicity make it advantageous for elderly people or patients with chronic illnesses who need regular medication.

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